

**AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE ORGANIZATION OF LABOR
RELATIONS IN LIGHT INDUSTRY AND MANUFACTURING
ENTERPRISES**

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***Abstract.** The article scientifically substantiates that light industry and manufacturing enterprises are an integral part of the organization of labor relations.*

***Keywords:** Labor law, light industry, production, enterprise, law, partnership system, working conditions, responsibility, consistency.*

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev said: “The task of forming a modern and broad-minded generation of young people who have a clear civic position, protect the interests of society and the state, and actively participate in changes and reforms. in the life of the people, of course, is extremely important” [3, p. 219]. It is necessary that each specialist has his own place. The organization of labor relations at light industry and manufacturing enterprises is important for ensuring the efficient operation of enterprises and protecting the interests of specialists. Labor legislation is the basis for regulating labor relations at light and manufacturing enterprises. It determines the rights and obligations of employers and employees, the procedure for concluding and executing employment contracts, working conditions, protection of workers’ rights, and mechanisms for resolving labor disputes.

The organization of labor relations at light industry and manufacturing enterprises is an integral part of their activities, contributes to the establishment of

stable and constructive relations between employers and employees, and also ensures compliance with legal norms and stability of production.

The right to work is one of the fundamental human rights and freedoms recognized in international documents. This right guarantees every person the opportunity to freely choose his place of work, receive equal pay for his work, and ensure safe and healthy working conditions. In addition, labor laws include a prohibition of forced labor and discrimination in the workplace on any basis. It should be noted that the right to work is not limited only to the opportunity to work, but also includes the right to vocational training and advanced training.

Respect for labor rights is the basis of social justice and sustainable development of society. It is therefore important that states and employers take the necessary measures to protect and respect this right of all citizens. The right to work is the basis of all human rights and freedoms. This is confirmed by the fact that today in our country the realization of human interests has become a high level of value, social protection of the population, and the full provision of labor rights of citizens are given attention at the level of state policy. . In this way, the necessary organizational and legal conditions are created, they are improved based on the requirements of the time, and the role of civil society institutions in this area increases. “Labor Code” [4], “On trade unions, guarantees of their rights and activities” [5], “On public associations in the Republic of Uzbekistan” [6], “On non-governmental non-profit organizations” [7] and more than two hundred laws and others normative documents provide a solid legal basis in this regard.

One of the basic principles of labor legislation in light industry and manufacturing enterprises is equal rights and opportunities for all workers, regardless of gender, age, race, nationality and other characteristics. Employers are obliged to comply with labor laws, provide employees with necessary working conditions, and protect them from discrimination and violation of their rights.

In addition, an important aspect of the organization of labor legislation at enterprises is ensuring labor protection and safety. Employers are required to provide workers with the necessary personal protective equipment, provide safety and industrial hygiene training, and create a safe work environment for all workers.

Thus, the organization of labor legislation in light industry and manufacturing enterprises in Russia plays a key role in ensuring fair and safe working conditions for all workers. Compliance with laws and protection of workers' rights are important to ensure industry stability and prosperous labor relations.

The source of Russian labor legislation is the Labor Code of the Russian Federation, adopted in 2001 [8]. This law defines the basic principles and rules in the field of labor relations between employees and employers, and also regulates the procedure for concluding and executing employment contracts. The Labor Code contains provisions on the labor rights and obligations of the parties, as well as the procedure for resolving labor disputes.

Collective bargaining agreements and agreements between trade unions and employers are also an important source of labor law. They can expand the rights of employees and establish additional guarantees and benefits not provided for by law.

In addition, labor standards can be determined and supplemented by orders and regulations of employers, internal labor regulations of enterprises and organizations.

In general, the sources of labor legislation in Russia provide balanced regulation of labor relations and protection of the interests of workers and employers. They contribute to the creation of a stable and fair environment for all participants in the labor process.

In Germany, labor law in light industry and manufacturing plays a key role in ensuring fair working conditions for workers. The organization of this right in

enterprises is of great importance for maintaining order and ensuring harmonious relations between employers and employees [9].

In Germany, labor law strictly regulates labor relations and defines the rights and obligations of both employers and employees. An important place is given to trade unions and collective agreements that protect the interests of workers and regulate working conditions at enterprises.

Compliance with labor laws at light industry and manufacturing enterprises helps create comfortable working conditions, increase labor productivity and reduce conflict between parties. It also helps to attract and retain qualified employees, which is an important factor in the success of the enterprise.

Thus, the organization of labor legislation in light industry and manufacturing enterprises in Germany plays an important role in ensuring business stability and efficiency, as well as improving working conditions and protecting workers' rights. The hourly wage was last set at 12 euros in October 2022 [10].

In the modern world, the organization of labor legislation in US light industry and manufacturing enterprises plays an important role in ensuring fair working conditions for workers. This includes protecting workers' rights in the workplace, regulating working hours, paying workers' wages, and ensuring occupational safety and health. A 2011 California law prohibits gender equality and discrimination [11].

Under US law, workers are entitled to a minimum wage, certain hours, paid vacation, sick days and holidays. In addition, employers must ensure safe working conditions and provide personal protective equipment.

The organization of labor legislation in US light industry and manufacturing enterprises helps to preserve the health and well-being of workers, increase labor productivity, and improve product quality. Therefore, it is important to comply with all labor laws and regulations to ensure fair working conditions for all workers.

The source of American labor law is the body of laws governing the relationship between employees and employers. The basis of this right is the Federal Labor Law, which defines the rights and obligations of the parties to labor relations.

Collective bargaining agreements between unions and employers are also an important element of American labor law. They determine working conditions and the protection of workers' rights.

In Sweden, the organization of labor legislation in light industry and manufacturing enterprises has its own characteristics and characteristics. Sweden is known for its progressive social policies and attention to workers.

More information about the Singapore Labor Code can be found at the following links [13].Singapore government agencies actively monitor compliance with labor laws in businesses, conducting inspections and audits to protect workers' rights and ensure compliance with laws and regulations.

During our research, we paid special attention to the extent to which students need to know labor relations in the light industry and manufacturing enterprises. In this case, the student:

Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1], Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2], Government resolutions directly regulating labor relations [14, 384 p.], collective agreements of manufacturing enterprises in the field of light industry [15, 80 p.], From a pedagogical point of view based on the need to know about internal labor regulations, other internal documents, employment contracts and their content, the basic standards that students have in the field of labor and technology. construction of light industry products should be studied in the science of labor law, which made it possible to determine the topics of new science-based lectures and seminars, as well as areas of self-study.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2023. – 80 p.
2. Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2023.
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Development strategy of the new Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2022. – P. 219.
4. Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. April 30, 2023 <https://lex.uz/docs/6257288>.
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On trade unions, guarantees of their rights and activities.” March 8, 2020 <https://lex.uz/acts/18156>.
6. Law “On public associations in the Republic of Uzbekistan”. February 15, 1991. No. 223-XII. <https://lex.uz/acts/111825>.
7. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On non-governmental non-profit organizations”. <https://www.lex.uz/acts/11360>. April 21, 2021 Law No. ORQ-683 amending certain legal documents. <https://lex.uz/docs/5388561?ONDATE=02/11/2024&ONDATE2=12/01/2023&action=compare>.
8. Labor Code of the Russian Federation. – Moscow, 2001. https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_34683.
9. Frekman A. Temporary employment business in Germany. 2004 15(1). Review of international companies and commercial law 7.